

Review

Social exclusion, restiveness and youth violence

MUSA AISHAT SULEIMAN

Department of Sociology, AL-Qalam University, Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author E-mail: musasuleiman2420@gmail.com

Received 2 September 2019; Accepted 22 November, 2019

This paper examines youth restiveness with specific examples from socially excluded communities across the nation and the challenges it brings to the socio-political and economic system cum the willing foreign investors and investments. This work relies heavily on secondary sources of data; to examine the activities of youth violence in the country. Some of these youth gangs are the Yandaba in Kano state, Area boys in Lagos, Kauraye in Katsina, and of course the Niger Delta militants, the Mosob in the east and a host of others in some parts of the country. These are restive youths due to an unequal distribution of the socio-political and economic resources of the country. When socially excluded youths cannot depend on those institutions designed to protect them, violence becomes an instrument to achieve certain outcomes, such as justice, security and economic gains. When conventional methods

of obtaining and working for increased social status, higher incomes and wider influence are limited, as they are often are, in marginalized communities, consequently, they are compelled to resort to violent actions and behaviors. Thus youth violence and violence interact in a vicious circle that leaves the youth in a hostile social situation, where the borders between legal and illegal, legitimate and illegitimate are not clear and uncertain. The use of violence by these youths who are in the minority affects the lives of the majority of the people, who do not resort to violence, thereby disrupting economic activities, thus affecting human and capital development negatively.

Keywords: Youth, restiveness, violence, exclusion, sustainable development

INTRODUCTION

As rightly observed, approximately between 15 to 20 years, we have witness a series of economic, social and political transformation that have change the pattern of youth violence. Movement within the regions, including migrations from rural areas, related rapid urbanization, institutional changes and that characteristic of modern sectors growth, reinforce the historical, reliance of many on informal mechanisms and transition for survival. The judicial and law enforcement system have weakly adapted to new challenges and continue to leave large segment of society within adequate access to justice, economic and physical security. It is important to state that the human society and in fact the entire universe is simply and squarely a composite entity. To this extent, individuals and groups have their own complexities,

needs, aspirations, hopes goals, opinions, views and values which could be social, economic, religious, psychological or political (Anioke, 2002). Hence, violence is bound to occur which presupposes that since conflict is a situation that is natural to man; our social life revolves and grows in conflict and violence.

The Kauraye of Katsina State, Yandaba of Kano, Odua people's congress, of south western states, MOSSOB, MOSOP, MEND and other ethnic cleavages abound, are getting out of proportion and each with its own motives, respectively. The invasion of old companies, the kidnapping and abduction of high chiefs and foreign nationals, the incessant harassment of traders in Lagos, everyday clashes in Jos, Nasarawa, e.t.c. the issue of indigene, setter questions that cut across the federation

is a thing of concern. The continuous clashes between the Fulani herdsmen and farmers, all these things pose a lot of threat to the ideals of sustainable democratic government and by extension the modern industrial sustainable development. The composite unemployment in the country increased from 38% in December 2001 to 42% in the first half of 2006 (Chukwuemeka, 2003). Despite the average figure it is noted to be high, as well higher in other states of the country, for example, it would be higher in Katsina than in Lagos. That is, Structural unemployment results in talent not being used where they are available, and as the saying goes that an idle mind is certainly the devil's workshop. As rightly observed, the situation has degenerated between the years 1999 to 2007 which led to declaration of curfew in some states of the federation (Chukwuemeka, 2008). The activities of Boko Haram, mostly in the states of Northern Nigeria, are a thing of concern to the nation. Northern states, by their nature and Geographical location give them an added advantage, by making them the food baskets of the nation; they are agrarian in nature. Consequently, there would be shortage supply of agricultural raw materials to the agricultural base industries. Under the menace of Boko Haram, food scarcity, lives and property were destroyed, industries were short down, and educational institutions could not function as at when due, which certainly affects development of the country.

CONCEPTUAL DEFINITIONS

Young adult males between the ages of 15-25 are generally the most violent groups (UNICEF, 2006). Youth simply refers to a young person between childhood and adult age. It is a transition period between adolescent and adulthood (Adegun and Akomolafe, 2013). To UNESCO; youth is better understood as a period of transition from the dependence as members of a community. Youth is a term used for sexes, male and female of a young age. There is no generally accepted definition of the specific age range of youth. Youth can begin as early as elementary school and last until the age of 21. Those between 14 and 15 are considered youth while people between 26 and 28 are youthful adults (Sayyid, 1990). The national youth development policy (2001) defines youth as people aged 18-25. They constitute about 40 percent of the more than 140 million people in Nigeria. The total population of youth between the ages of 10-24 in Nigeria was 45.4 million in 2006 which is 24 percent of the total population.

Violence is generally described as an intentional use of force or power with a predetermined and by which one or more persons produce physical, mental (psychological) or sexual injury, injure the freedom of movement or cause the death of another person or persons (UNDP, 2006). Restiveness has been defined as the act of being unable

to stay still or unwillingness to be controlled, especially because you feel bored or not satisfied with something (Patrick et al., 2013). It has also been described as a sustained protestation embarked upon to enforce desired outcome from a constituted authority by an organized body of youth (Elegbeleye, 2017). It is marked violence and description of youth activities. Youth violence relates to matters of agitation by youths over issues of deprivation, neglect, marginalization and feelings of dissatisfaction. The engagement of youths in agitations for the restoration of their rights and dignity or self-seeking and criminal activities, that can be either constructive (positive) or destructive (negative) to the use and dump mentality and attitude of those considered to be involved in acts of oppression and repression against their interest. It is equally a deliberate instrument of organized responses to perceived grievances that has an increasing potency and capability for destruction. Cardinal, youth restiveness as a manifestation of anxiety that encompasses the dysfunctional effects of anxiety on human body and the description of the psychological activities of the body that gives vent to anxiety. It is in fact a sustained protestation embarked upon with an eye to enforcing a desired outcome from a constituted authority by an organized body of youths. It is thus, an excess behavior attributed that is commonly marked by violence and destruction of lawful activities (Ejumudo, 2014).

GENESIS OF YOUTH VIOLENCE IN NIGERIA

Studies have shown that youths are responsible for 90-95% of conflict in Nigeria (Omeje, 2005). The history of Nigeria is replete with instances of youth restiveness. For example was the description of the parliament in Lagos by the Nigeria students from the University of Ibadan and Yaba Polytechnic in order to prevent law-makers from ratifying an Anglo-Nigeria defense pact which was imposed by the British government as a condition for granting Nigeria independence (Chukuezi, 2009). Youths also participated in the civil war between 1967 and 1970 Nairaland, (1960). Other instances of violence after the civil war are: in the 1980 in the month of May, religious riot/violence in Zaria, in which lives and properties were destroyed. December 18-20, riots in Kano by the maitatsine sect, 4,177 were killed. In 1982, the months of September 29, October 3, disturbances in Kaduna, Kaduna State, 53 people were killed and many churches were burnt. In 1982, October 29-30, further trouble in Maiduguri, Borno State by the maitatsine sects leading to the death of 118 people. In 1984, February 27, March 5, disturbances in Yola, Adamawa State by the by the maitatsine sect 568 people died. In 1985, April 26-28, riot in Gombe, Bauchi State involving the maitatsine sect left 105 people dead. In 1986, March, Palm Sunday Christians and Muslim clashed during processions in Ilorin

Kwara state. In 1986, may at the University of Ibadan, Muslims burned the figure of the Risen Christ at the Catholic chapel of the resurrection. 1987, March 5, in Kafanchan, Kaduna state, Christians and Muslim clashed at the college of Education, churches and mosques were burned. In 1987 March, in Katsina, Funtua, Zaria, Gusau and Kaduna, (Kaduna State) a wave of religious riot was witnessed, many churches were burned, many lives lost and property destroyed. In 1991, April in Bauchi State over 200 lives were lost and property destroyed. In 1991 October 14-15 in Kano, the attempt of the Izala sect to stop Rev. Bonnke from preaching became violent. Thousands of lives were lost and property destroyed.

In 1992, February 6 and then May 15-16 in Zango Kataf, Zaria, Kaduna State, a common clash become religious with live lost and property destroyed. In Funtua, Katsina State the Kalakoto religious sects assaulted a village head, 50 lives were lost and property destroyed in reprisal attacks. In 1994 may 21, a mob killed four men in Ogoni land eventually, Ken Saro-wiwa was hanged for allegedly being behind this. In 1999, may 20 Muslim-Christian riots in Kaduna, for three days several hundreds were feared dead. In 1999, may 29 the Itse Kiri fought in the Delta region over 200 were killed. In 1999 July 18, Hausa and Yoruba rioted in Shagamu, over 60 people were killed. This led to unrest in Kano where over 70 were killed. On August 11, about 200 were killed as the army intervened in Taraba state. On November 25, Yoruba and Hausa clashed in Lagos, about 1000 were killed.

On November 8, kidnapping of policemen by the Egbesu boys in Odi, Bayelsa State. On 2000 January, clash between the Odua people congress (OPC) and the police in Lagos State, a divisional Police officer was killed, February riot in Kaduna over the introduction of sharia, over 400 were killed. On September 7, Christians-Muslims conflicts in Jos over 500 were killed. 2001 October 12-14, in Kano, there were anti-American riot because of USA intervention in Afghanistan; at least 350 people were killed. On October 12-19, soldiers were killed after feuds near Benue and Taraba states from October 21-22, Massacre 7200 civilians in Benue by soldiers in retaliation for the 19 soldiers who were killed. No one was held accountable for the massacre. On 2002, December 23, youth Democratic movement embarked on a rampage, burning the NNPC building in Ikoyi Lagos. 2003, March 22, Militant Ijaw youths made attempts for resources control in Warri Delta State, killing two soldiers and injuring two others. On April 25, the same group intercepted the communication network of the Army and Navy and had a shootout with them, leaving 10 officers dead. This list is almost in exhaustive, other instances of violence involving youths which are not in the list include political clashes and anonymous killings, assassinations etc. in 2009, the dreaded Boko Haram sect started a series of attack involving bombings of worship places, kidnapping and taking hostages etc. the menace of the sect and the hideout of militant groups in the Niger Delta

still continue till date in Nigeria.

FACTORS THAT BRING ABOUT YOUTH VIOLENCE IN NIGERIA

Youth violence is a creation of so many factors with a difference from one environment to another. Nigeria is not an exception, however certain constant factors breed and nature youth violence, some of these factors will be examined, such as the question of ethnic Naturalization and the formation of ethnic militants, the desire to wrestle power coupled with other consideration have led to increase ethnic nationalism among the minority ethnic groups, while the larger ethnic groups are equally strongly attached to their peculiar beliefs necessitating increased nationalism within them sometimes their activities are carried in a manner that has led to violent act. The case of Odua People's congress (OPC) and the movement for the advancement of sovereign state of Biafra (MOSSOB) while various minority groups such as the Ijwa youths council (IYC) middle belt forum among others, have been challenging the activities of the dominant ethnic groups. These competitors have ended in ethnic militant attack and clashes. As it was rightly observed by Akinboye, (2001) the youths constitute the lots of these ethnic militias. The role of elites, they constitute a strong class of capitalist who depend on the state machinery for survival (Joseph, 1999) as well as major players in the ethnic games for exploitation and manipulation of the non-elite, often the case directed towards personal or elite group interest which mostly promotes division and hatred among people in multi-cultural societies such as Nigeria (Otite, 1990). The sources of youth violence differ from one environment to another. In Nigeria, certain constant factors breed and nurture youth violence, some of these factors are as follows;

Social and moral decadence

Youth restiveness appears to be the symptoms of the social and moral decadence of the Nigerian society in general. This decay manifests itself in the form of various social vices and ills epitomized by corruption, indiscipline, moral laxity and many other ills in the society (Ifaturoti, 1994:155). Therefore, since youths in Nigeria, who do not exist in a vacuum, observe this unhealthy social environment and the breakdown in societal values and norms, it is from what they observe and the signals they perceive that they, in order to achieve what they perceive as societal goals, emulate the behavior of the society. Thus, the society in this way can be seen as the source of restiveness, for the youths merely reflect societal behavior. In a society where persons who have achieved success through corruption are lauded, the signal sent to the youths is that corruption is an acceptable means of achieving success (Ifaturoti, 1994: 155). This is of course

reflected in the restive behavior of youths.

Influence of peer group

Peer group pressure and the age factor play an important role in determining youth involvement in restive act. The average age group of youth is between 15 and 25 years. Many youths of this age grade are at their most impressionistic and they tend to imitate easily. Thus, they are more easily manipulated and influenced by their peers, who encourage them to commit delinquent acts on the grounds that it enhances their status and commitment in the society (Tamuno, 1991:144).

Culture of drug abuse

The prevailing culture of drug abuse has in no small measure contributed to the upsurge in youth violence. Hard drugs such as heroin, marijuana and cocaine are often found in their possession. Violent act clashes often occur under the influence of alcohol and other mind disturbing drug influence. Ifaturoti, (1994:156) attests to the fact that abuse of drugs, such as cocaine, and over-indulgence in alcoholic drinks, such as gin and whisky, alter the state of the user's mind and predispose to violence.

Role of mass media

The mass media has also contributed to the upsurge in youth violence in Nigeria. The importation of violent films, which are shown on television and the everyday brutalities of Nigerian life, such as cult clashes, assassination and public violence, written about by the media with all the gory details and photographs, merge the frontiers of fantasy with reality for youths. It is possible that many of these delinquent youths merely act out what they have seen on video or television.

Ethnic nationalism and the formation of ethnic militias

The desire to wrestle the power coupled with other considerations have led to increased ethnic nationalism among the minority ethnic groups, while the larger ethnic groups are equally, strongly attached to their peculiar beliefs necessitating increased nationalism within them. Sometimes their activities are carried out in a manner that has led to youth restiveness. The cases of Odua People Congress OPC (Yoruba) and Movement for the Advancement of Sovereign State of Biafra MASSOB (Igbo) represent a good example of this perspective, while various minority ethnic groups such as Ijaw Youth

Council (IYC), Middle Belt Forum among others, have been challenging the activities of the dominant ethnic groups. These competitions have ended up in ethnic militant attacks and ethnic clashes. However, it has been revealed that the youths constitute the bulk of these ethnic militias (Akinboye, 2001:176).

Role of the elites

The elites in Nigeria have promoted youth violence. They represent essentially capitalists who depend on the state machinery for survival (Joseph, 1999:16). They are also major player in the ethnic game for exploitation and manipulation of non-elites, usually directed towards personal/elite group's interests, which mostly promotes division and hatred among people in pluralistic societies (Oтите, 1990:210). In many other instances, the elites often sponsor youths in ethno-religious, political and cult violence. Such situation sets an appalling role model for youths and increases their vulnerability to or penchant for violent crime.

Economic factor

According to Obateru, (1994:132), poverty apparently accounts for the bulk of restive acts due to such problems as unemployment, inadequate housing, physical and social infrastructures. The current depression in the Nigerian economy must have worsened the situation of youths; this has rendered the youths idle and almost hopeless, hence they have become instruments of manipulation by the elites for ethno-religious and political insurrections.

Urban congestion

This has contributed to the promotion of youth restiveness and violence in Nigeria, especially in the cities. A greater proportion of Nigerians live in the cities. The rapid rate of urban agglomeration was caused by the superior employment, education, health care and other attractions of the urban environment. Most of these urban migrants are youths (Ndegwa, 1992:92). Therefore, the increase in the rate of youth rural-urban drift complicates the problems of housing, employment and population in the cities. All these problems produce stresses and strains that can be later expressed in the form of riots, cult clashes, and vandalism and so on.

Family influence

Family influence plays an undeniable role in shaping the characters of youths. The quality of their family life is

reflected in their behavior. In families where violence is a way of life, a reflection of it is seen in the violent behavior of the youth of the family (Ifaturoti, 1994:157). Elaborating on this fact, Renovize (1978), Oliver and Taylor, (1971), Scott (1974), Levine, (1975) observed that children living in violent homes are themselves more likely to become agents of violence as they grow up. These children naturally see violence as an instrument of inter-group relations. It is also possible for the frequently battered mother to transfer her suffering to her children in the form of harsh punishments for minor offences. Such children soon become resistant to even dangerous battering and gladly participate in street/public fight (Albert, 1994:71). They become threats to peace and harmony in the society as they are recruited into gangster organizations, especially if they are unrestricted by being exposed to violent films. Moreover, because many parents do not pay enough attention to the children, youths disturbed by such family situation may indulge in delinquent acts as a way of either seeking the parents' attention to rebelling against such parents (Ifaturoti, 1994:157).

YOUTH RESTIVENESS IN NIGERIA'S FOURTH REPUBLIC (1999 TO DATE)

Nigeria, with the opening of yet another chapter of democratic rule in 1999 has been faced with several acts of violence perpetrated by youths. These restive acts have taken the forms of murder, cult clashes, armed robbery, theft, bombing, ethnic militancy, intra and inter party clashes and so on. The alarming rate of youth violence during the period emanated from the problems such as poverty, economic frustration, resulting especially from widespread unemployment among young people, political conflicts as well as failure of government to punish the perpetrators of violence. From 1999 to 2004, several people have been killed in various restive acts perpetrated majorly by youths in Nigeria. While the examples of these incidents are in-exhaustive, the significant categories of these restive violent acts and their nature are vividly captured in the (Table 1).

Implications for sustainable democracy and development

From (Table 1), it can be deduced that youth restiveness in Nigeria during the period under review embraced inter and intra party clashes, ethnic militant attack, bombing and cult clashes. One important thing to be mentioned about the phenomenon of secret cultism is that the menace has transcended the university campuses recently. Campus cultists had recruited youth from outside the schools. Cases of frequent cult clashes in Nigeria have been reported (Muhammad, 2005). Evidences arising from the above capitulation also show that 1999 to 2002

witnessed a cyclical instability, marked by the frequent eruption of politically motivated youth restiveness. The prevalence of one political restiveness or another has been the mainstay of Nigeria, with youths as the major actors in the theatre of restive conflicts.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Although there are several theories for explaining facts generated in research endeavors, for the purpose of this study, the "Strain Theory of Deviance and the Frustration Theory" were adopted. This became expedient because all the factors that are commonly advanced as an explanation for youth violence can be located in the above context due to the fact that they all relate to the bottom line, which is dissatisfaction and unrealized goals. The "Strain" theory as propounded by Merton, (1968) contends that deviant behavior results not from pathological personalities; rather, it is a consequence of the culture and structure of society itself. He reasoned that because all members of the society are placed in different strata of the social structure, they do not have the same access to the realization of their shared values and goals. The shared values and goals translate into cultural goals which could be material possession, educational attainment, and significant others. Merton further noted that people feel strained when they are incapable of meeting the cultural goals to which they are exposed owing to inaccessibility to the culturally approved and acceptable means of realizing the goals. The tendency therefore is to resort to deviant and unacceptable means.

In the same vein, the "Frustration" theory presupposes that a continuing or unresolved motivational conflict is a source of frustration (Atkinson and Atkinson, 1975). This theory argues that when a person's progress toward a desired goal is blocked, delayed, or otherwise interfered with, he or she encounters frustration. Blocked goal seeking therefore produces confusion, bewilderment, and annoyance. Frustration, by implication, connotes an event rather than an emotional state; thwarting circumstances rather than their consequences. Apart from the various types of conflict that provide a major source of human frustration, there are other barriers to the satisfaction of drives (Atkinson and Atkinson, 1975). Frustration, whether it is as the result of obstacles, deficiencies, or conflict, has both immediate and remote consequences. This viewpoint is premised on the reasoning that when blocked in goal seeking, the individual or youth may react immediately or develop attitudes toward uncertainty or risk taking that has more enduring consequences. Restlessness and tensions are usually associated with many actions indicating unhappiness, dissatisfaction, and frustration and closely related to increased tensions; and restless movements are the rage states that lead to destructiveness and hostile

Table 1. Cases of youth restiveness in Nigeria from (1999-2004).

Perpetrators	Motives	Date/Place	Nature of Act	Targets/ casualty
Egbesu Boys	Revenge	November 8, 1999. Odi Bayelsa State	Kidnapping and killing of policemen	Security agents
Odua People Congress OPC	Revenge/ clash between OPC member and police	January 2000, Bariga Lagos	Abduction & Murder	Divisional police officer (DPO) for Bariga was egregiously killed
Anonymous	Political fanaticism	February 22, 2001 Enugu State	Shooting & assassination Attempt	Abel Chuckwu speaker of the Enugu State House of Assembly
Anonymous	Political fanaticism	December 23, 2001 South Western State of Oyo.	Assassination	Federal Justice Minister and Attorney General Bola Ige
Anonymous	Political fanaticism	August, 15 2002 Ilorin enroute to Abuja	Assassination	The Kwara State Chairman of the PDP, Ahmed Pategi, and a police orderly were killed in a vehicle
Anonymous	Political fanaticism	August 30, 2002 Abia State	Failed bomb attack	Broadcasting Corporation of Abia , BCA
Anonymous	Political intolerance	September 2, 2002 Anambra State	Ambush/ass-assassination & murder	Barnaba Igwe, Chairman of the branch of Nigerian Bar Association and his wife Abigail Amaka Igwe
Youth Democratic Movement YDM	Injustice in Niger Delta	December 23, 2002 Ikoyi Lagos	Arson	NNPC building; the fire burnt most of the computers software and hardware used by the corporation
Anonymous	Political fanaticism	March 3, 2003 Rivers State	Assassination	Dr Marshall Isokoari Harry, the National Vice-Chairman for the South-South zone of the ANPP
Militant Ijaw Youths	Self-determination/resource control	March 22, 2003 Warri south-west local government area Delta State	Clashes with soldiers	Two soldiers were killed and two others injured.
Militant Ijaw Youths	Self-determination & resource control	April 25, 2003 Warri, Delta State	Shooting/ armed attack	10 Navy, Army died. Their radio communication intercepted
Militant Ijaw Youths	Self-determination	April 30, 2003 Warri Delta State	Shooting & Murder	Five women were killed in a cross-fire between the militants and government security agents
Ijaw militants	Self-determination	May 1, 2003. Opumani Tank farm, Okerenkoko, Delta State	Armed attack, hostage-taking and murder	Government forces and oil installations

Militant youths from Binioni	Self determination Resource control agitation	November 2003. Foropo-Bakolga Local Council Bayelsa State	Hostage-taking	Targeted oil platforms. One of the militants was killed and an oil worker wounded during the rescue operation by the Nigerian Navy.
Niger Delta militant youths	Self-determination/ resource control agitation	November 2003, Niger Delta	Hostage-taking	Oil platforms
Anonymous	Political cause	November 15 2003 Ilorin metropolis	Explosive bombing	National Pilot Newspaper office. The building was destroyed, five employees injured
Niger Delta militant youths	Self-determination, resource control agitation	November 27, 2003. Niger Delta	Kidnapping	Oil platforms
Taliban operatives	Religious fanaticism	January 1, 2004 Yobe State	Arson	The N100 million Tarmuwa local government secretariat.
Taliban operatives	Religious fanaticism	January 15 2004, Kanamma and Geidan Local Government area Yobe State.	Murder/ vandalism	Civilian population and government security agents.
Taliban operatives	Religious fanaticism	September 21, 2004 Borno State	Murder and theft of ammunition	Bama police station, killing six police officers, and carted away ammunitions
s Taliban operatives	Religious fanaticism	September 21, 2004 Borno State	Murder/Arson	Gwoza police station, killed policemen and civilians
Taliban operatives	Fanaticism	September 22, 2004 Gwoza hills near Limankara village	Shooting	3 civilians were killed

Source: Adeoye and Muhammed AY (2005) restiveness in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

attacks that have become commonplace in the Nigerian environment. Although aggression is often the result of frustrating circumstances, an explanation of aggression based solely on environmental influences is incomplete. Because of the problems inherent in the original version of the frustration-aggression hypothesis, Berkowitz, (1965) suggested three alterations to the theory. He opined that emotional reaction does not compulsorily cause aggression, but it creates a predisposition for aggressive acts. The above reality is typical of the Nigerian youths who have little or no access to the environmental opportunities due to the insensitivity and neglect that characterize or underpin the activities and roles of the Nigerian state in an unholy alliance with national (local) and the international (foreign) bourgeoisie. Thus, the inability of the youths to actualize their goals through the institutionalized means in the face of the opportunities that abound in their environment has

produced strains and frustrations culminating in all shapes of social problems and deviant practices that consequently pose serious threats to our nascent democracy and sustainable development. The strain theory of deviance and the frustration theory therefore have the utilitarian explanatory value for the youth restiveness and the attendant militancy activities in Nigeria.

Implications on national development

Consequences of youth restiveness and violence can be devastating on both the socio-political and economic development of the nation. Youth restiveness has resulted in the destruction of both private and public property, physical and mental cases and to an extreme death. As rightly observed and mentioned in the body of

the paper, youth restiveness, led to the death of so many youths and the elderly too. Not only that the destruction worth millions of naira, this is to say that, it has led to revenue lost with a concomitant effect on social transformation and as well as slow down growth and sustainable development. Of paramount importance is the destruction of social relationships in the affected areas such as the incidence of the chibok girls, in Borno state of Nigeria. The abduction of the chibok girls resulted in world outcry. Some of the girls recovered are not without an issue such as unwanted pregnancy and other bodily harm. The worst is, some of them are used as instrument of terror attack, carrying and delivering improvised explosive devices to specified designated targets to detonate them on their persons, regardless of all others at the target. Extra-judicial killings/ brutality by uniformed men; 36 killed, 34 injured in 5 months. Nigeria appears to have become one huge killing field of defenseless citizens and the killing machines is made of uniformed men comprising the Nigeria police, military and other gun wielding security operatives who think it is no big deal shooting and killing the same people they are paid to protect (Daily trust, 2016) A worsen situation of youth restiveness is a clear indications and as well needless to say that something is wrong with the system . Logically to say the youths enjoyed restive violent act more than peaceful resolutions of a particular crisis. One cannot run away from the fact that the phenomenon of youth restiveness scares away investors and retards all ramifications of social change and sustainable development in the country. To further buttress the above point with the present attacks and destructions of petroleum pipelines in the Niger Delta region by the Niger Delta Avengers (NDA). It is therefore right to say that the neglect of youths in Nigeria's development plans has been one of the sources of youth restiveness, kenniston, (1971).

Conclusion

Here in this paper, we try to conceptualize youth's restiveness in the context within which the problem is produced in the country. The analysis shows that youth involvement in restive acts, as manifested is an evidence of social exclusion with the resultant effect of unemployment, poverty and child abuse, among other causative factors. Such restive acts pose a serious challenge to human and capital development. Therefore, the need to take urgent measures to address the menace is imperative. Towards addressing the problem of youth restiveness, the following suggestions are hereby proffered. First and foremost, governments at all levels must disassociate themselves from restive acts and from those who maintain their positions through coercion. There is no doubt that government that is insensitive will only continue to promote restiveness rather than reducing

the menace. Since the youths are the future leaders, special efforts should be made to encourage and promote activities that are of interest to young people in a way to promote tolerance, trust and cosmopolitanism among them. The call for the strengthening of cross religious and ethnic institutions for youth development programmes such as the National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) as well as sporting competitions is immeasurable. This apart, since youths constitute the bulk of ethnic militias, recruitment into their rank have been Akinboye facilitated by inability of the government to articulate coherent policies and programmes that are imperative for the development and maximum utilization of youths in the society (Akinboye, 2001:179). This has led to widespread disillusionment and frustration, which has culminated in the sustainability of the ethnic militias in the country. This situation calls for the creation of employment opportunities for the youth if the government is truly interested in finding a lasting solution to the situation, whereby short of which they have become ready tools in the hands of those perpetrators of communal feuds. The problem of restiveness could partly be dealt with using specially designed radio and television programmes, jingles and group discussions. Such programmes could be aimed at discouraging youth restiveness and violence. The menace of youth restiveness can also be arrested through the creation of an enabling environment for job, educational, healthcare delivery in the rural areas. This is necessary in order to reduce the rapid rate of rural-urban drift, especially among the youths .Furthermore, family and religious institutions have important roles to play in arresting upsurge in youth restiveness and crime. At the level of family, parents should be good role model for their children. They should eschew violence, pay enough attention to their children and avoid all forms of child abuse. Equally, religious organizations should be more pro-active in preventing and transforming youth restiveness through sermons, exhortations, preaching and provision of social as well as humanitarian services for the youths. If the above recommendations are adopted for action, it is believed that they will go a long way in curtailing and transforming the upsurge of youth violence in the society.

Author's declaration

I declare that this study is my research work and I agree to publish it in the journal.

REFERENCES

- Adegun OA and Akomolafe CO (2013) Entrepreneurship Education and Youth Empowerment in Contemporary Nigeria. Scholarly Journal of Education, 2 (5).
- Adeoye MN, Muhammed AY (2005). Terrorism in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: Implications for Sustainable Democracy and Development. Paper presented at the National Conference on Democracy and

- Development, organized by the Faculty of Business and Social Sciences University of Ilorin, April.
- Akinboye OS (2001). "The Matrix of Ethnicity and Ethno-Religious Crises in Nigeria's Nascent Democracy" in Agwoholobo, E. (ed.) *The Humanistic Management of Pluralism: A Formula for Development in Nigeria*. Lagos: Murtab Press for the Faculty of Arts, University of Lagos ALF Publication.
- Albert IO (1994). "Urban Violence in Contemporary Africa: Some Theoretical Explorations" in Albert IO et al. (eds.) *Urban Management and Urban Violence in Africa*. Ibadan:
- Anioke U (2002). "Conflict Resolution in the Local Government" paper Presented in a workshop, organised by Local Government Service Commission, Enugu.
- Atkinson JW, Atkinson RC (1975). *Fundamentals of psychology*. New York, NY: Wiley Press
- Berkowitz L (1965). Some aspects of observed aggression. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 2(3), 359-369. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0022221>
- Daily Trust, (2016) Daily Trust, 22nd may, 2016.
- Danjibo ND (2012) Islamic fundamentalism and sectarian violence ; the maitatsine and boko-haram crisis in Nigeria.
- Chukuezi CO (2009). Poverty and youth restiveness in Nigeria: Implications for national development. *Ozean Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(2):
- Chukwuemeka E (2003). *Principles of Human and Personnel management in Nigeria*, Enugu: HRV Publishers.
- Chukwuemeka E (2008). Re-branding the Niger Delta for Socio-economic Development, *Businessday Newspaper*, 7(11):
- Elegbeleye OS (2017). Recreational facilities in schools: A panacea for youths' restiveness. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 93-98.
- Ejumudo KBO (2014). Youth Restiveness in the Niger delta; a critical discourse; first published in May 1 2014. www.nairaland.com/798193/history-violence-nigeria-since-1960
- History of Violence in Nigeria Since 1960 (Green Whit Green, Where is the Red?) (2011)*. Retrieved March 22, 2015, from *Naira land Forum*.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2001). National development policy. 18 - 35 years youths.
- Ifaturoti TO (1994). "Delinquent Sub-culture and Violence in Nigerian Universities" in Albert, IO et al (eds.) *Urban Management and Urban Violence in Africa Vol. 2*. Ibadan: IFRA.
- Joseph RA (1999). *Democracy and Prebential Politics in Nigeria: The Rise and Fall of Second Republic*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Ltd.
- kenniston k (1971). *Youths and dissent; the rise of a new opposition*. harvest book.
- Levine MB (1975). "Interparental Violence and Its Effect on the Children: A Study of 50 Families in General Practice" *Medicine, Science and Law* 15 (3).
- Manning H, Truzz A (1972). *Youth and Sociology*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc.
- Merton RK (1968). *Social theory and social structure*. New York, NY: International Publishers.
- Mohammed AY (2005). "Youth and Urban Violence in Nigeria A Reflection on the Contemporary Ilorin Township" in Ayinla, S.A. (ed.) *Issues in Political Violence in Nigeria*. Ilorin: Hamson Ltd.
- Ndegwa P (1992). "Africa and the World: Africa on Its Own in Africa Rise to Challenge" in Obasanjo O, Mosha FGN (eds.) *Africa Leadership Forum*. Abeokuta: ALF Publications.
- Obateru OI (1994). "Planning the City to Mitigate Urban Violence" in Albert, .I.O et. al (eds.) *Urban Management and Urban violence in Africa*. Vol.1. Ibadan: IFRA.
- Oliver JE, Taylor E (1971). "Five Generations of ill-treated Children in One Family Pedigree" *British Journal of Psychiatry*. 119-437-80.
- Omeje K (2005). *Youths, Conflicts and Perpetual Instability in Nigeria*. Retrieved March 22, 2015, from *Holler Africa: www.hollerafrica.com*
- Otite O(1990). *Ethnic pluralism and ethnicity in Nigeria; with comparative materials*.
- Patrick O, Arisi RO, Osah MI (2013). Youth restiveness and insecurity in Niger Delta: A focus on Delta State. *Global Journal of Human Social Science* 13:49.
- Renovize J (1978). *Web of violence; a study of family violence*. harmonds worth; penguin books ltd.
- Sayyid MM (1990). *Youth and morals* (p. 7). Tehran: Islamic Culture Development Office.
- Scott PD (1974). "Battered Wives" *British Journal of Psychiatry* 125:433-41.
- Tamuno T (1991). *Peace and Violence in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Longman.
- UNDP (2006). *Youth and Violent Conflict; Society and Development in Crisis*. New York.